

**PRESIDENTIAL, CREATIVE AND SPECIALIZED SCHOOL
MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**

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Annotation: *This article discusses the new opportunities and innovations in the educational system of modern educational institutions for the children of our country.*

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Speaking about the President, creativity and specialized schools, the head of our state said. At the heart of the focus on the system of specialized schools is the education of students as innovative and creative thinking, modern staff, high spirituality. New and modern educational institutions have opened the door to new opportunities for the education of children in our country.

It is gratifying to see the innovations and developments in all areas, which are currently undergoing extensive reforms. In particular, the changes in the education system are attracting the attention not only of us, but also of other countries and international experts.

One of such huge changes in the system is that the first Presidential schools were launched in a short period of time in accordance with the Presidential Decree of February 20, 2019 "On measures to establish presidential schools."

The President signed a Decree and Resolution on the creation of a single and effective system aimed at working with talented young people, supporting their initiatives to realize their talents and potential.

A meeting chaired by Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 17, 2022, dedicated to the priorities of radically improving the quality of education and upbringing in specialized schools began. At the meeting, the President gave instructions to industry officials and regional governors.

It is noted that by 2025 it is planned to increase GDP to \$ 100 billion and increase exports to \$ 30 billion.

To do this, first of all, we need to prepare a patriotic young generation that meets modern requirements and is equipped with the necessary knowledge, logical thinking, leadership skills, - said the President.

The educational process in the presidential schools is carried out according to the program "STEAM - education" (Science - natural sciences, Technology - technologies, Engineering - technical creativity, Art - art, Mathematics - mathematics).

This will allow talented young people to develop thinking skills, will, creative potential, flexibility. Classes in this area are conducted entirely in English. Currently, the school is provided with textbooks and manuals on the STEAM methodology.

The school is built in a modern style, in accordance with international standards. There is a large library in the center of the science center. It is natural that this library has a book fund that will help the next generation to acquire thorough knowledge.

The management of such modern schools requires special skills and great competence, as well as the study of modern management achievements from developed foreign countries. The administrative staff of the Presidential, Creative and Specialized Schools is based on the existing traditional school management structure of the Republic, where the Executive Director (1), the Director of Academic Affairs (1), the Deputy Director for Special Sciences (1), the Spiritual - Deputy Director for Enlightenment (1), Deputy Director for Military-Patriotic and Pre-Conscription Youth Training (1), Chief Accountant (1), Personnel Manager (1).

In addition, the school has hired teachers from abroad: in collaboration with the Canadian recruitment company Teach Away and the British recruitment company TIC Recruitment, 30 foreign specialists have been selected for the school. 72 experienced and qualified local teachers were also involved. All of them passed a special exam. Specialists who are selected for such schools should not only have in-depth knowledge, but also high pedagogical skills. In this way, candidates who fully meet our requirements have started working with our experienced mentors. The first results are not bad. Students not only enrich their theoretical knowledge, but also participate in clubs such as swimming, chess, music, dance, organized on the basis of their interests. Individual engagement with each student is the main goal of the school administration. Among the students are young people who have achieved high results in mathematics. In order to further enrich their knowledge, it is planned to involve the most experienced, knowledgeable mathematicians of the Academy of Sciences. In addition, efforts are being made to ensure that students participate in international science Olympiads. It is planned to attract to our school

educated young people who came to our country with gold medals in science olympiads, and to create conditions for them to teach their experiences to children.

Graduates of presidential schools will receive a duly certified state certificate, a certificate, as well as a diploma of the relevant program at the international level (International Baccalaureate, Advanced Placement or International Advanced Levels). This provides access to leading higher education institutions in foreign countries. Depending on which profession students choose in the future, they will be directed to this field. However, no matter what profession students choose, literature, art and music are taught in depth so that they have a broad outlook. The reason is that our representatives, who went abroad on behalf of Uzbekistan, have their own opinion and worldview in all areas.

That is why he organized debates in schools, where children can freely express their views on the topic. All of this is controlled by strong educators. Imagine, for example, that if a student is well versed in physics but is unable to communicate his knowledge to the public, and his knowledge remains only in a paper and written article, the people will not be interested in it. Children in these schools, on the other hand, have no difficulty in applying it, either in theory or in practice. Because these debates also teach him to express his opinion correctly.

All this will help the younger generation to grow up with a well-educated, broad and healthy outlook.

New and modern educational institutions have opened the door to new opportunities for the education of children in our country.

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